

Research Article

Level Of Gender-Based Violence In Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City Of Samal, Davao Del Norte, Philippines

Lovely G. Boncales¹, Sheena Mae T. Mariamonte¹, Rena D. Morales¹, Venes Jay B. Tito¹, Christopher V. Famor²,

¹Bachelor of Public Administration , Samal Island City College , Philippines

²Department of Forestry, University of Southeastern Philippines , Tagum-Mabini Campus .

Abstract: Gender-based violence remains a pressing issue in the Philippines despite the implementation of special penal laws such as the Republic Act 9262, which upholds the rights of women and children. As of 2024, three cases of violence against women were recorded in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal. This study used Pearson's r to examine the correlation between the level of gender-based violence and community awareness. A sample of 284 respondents was determined using Slovin's formula and proportional allocation, then selected through simple random sampling. Data was gathered using a modified survey questionnaire. Findings revealed that the level of gender-based violence was very low, with 250 respondents reporting "Never" experiencing it (Mean=1.22).

On the other hand, awareness of the provisions of R.A. 9262 was relatively high, as 167 respondents were "Moderately Aware" (Mean=3.83). However, the correlation between the level of gender-based violence and awareness was only weakly positive ($r=0.27$; $p<0.001$), suggesting that higher awareness of R.A. 9262 may contribute to a decrease in gender-based violence. The study highlights the importance of strengthening community education on R.A. 9262 and violence against women (VAW). It recommends impartiality among researchers, the appointment of guidance counselors to ensure participants' well-being, and collaboration with organizations to boost awareness campaigns. Additionally, it encourages the use of digital media to challenge gender stereotypes and sustain advocacy efforts.

Keywords: R.A. 9262, women's rights, awareness, Gender and Development, women empowerment, women's welfare

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Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTINGS

This chapter comprises the background of the study, statement of the problem, theoretical framework, conceptual framework, scope and delimitation, significance of the study, and definition of terms.

Background of the Study

The United Nations has circumscribed gender-based violence as "acts that inflict physical, mental, sexual harm or suffering, threats of such acts, coercion and other deprivations of liberty" (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees [UNCHR], 2024). Violent acts can happen everywhere at any given time, regardless of race and societal background, and women are more vulnerable, making it a worldwide societal concern in 3 out of 5 women in their lifetime (World Vision, 2022).

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A report conducted by the Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) in 2023 argues that to grapple with the escalating rate of violence across genders, the main advocacy of women's empowerment should be to subscribe to all legal forms that aim to fully diminish the discrimination based on gender, especially against women in developing countries. Moreover, an estimated at least half a billion of the population under the age of 15 have been victimized by sexual and physical abuse and sexual violence by non-partners or conceivably experience it in their lifespan (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021).

The Philippines Statistics Authority's National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) study states that Filipinas aged between 15 and 49 who are in romantic relationships are the ones who suffer from physical, sexual, or emotional abuse. Furthermore, considering that the Philippines already has laws protecting women, such as the Republic Act No. 9262 or also known as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act, its increase in physical violence cases with 8,399, with 1,791 reported cases of rape, and 1,505 reported cases of acts of obscenities has been concerning (Philippine Statistics Authority [PSA], 2017).

When compared to 2021, Violence Against Women and Their Children (VAWC) acts regarding the number of reported cases of cases in Davao City have increased to almost 2,000 instances in 2022. Additionally, three regrettable occurrences of women and children violence were filed to the Punong Barangay office of Barangay Tagbaobo of Island Garden City of Samal in 2024 via a blotter submitted by the complainants, who were also barangay residents (Patumbon, 2023).

Moreover, existing special penal laws, such as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children, also known as Republic Act No. 9262, were passed in order to these delicate and concerning issues of "gender-based violence" (GBV) in order to protect women and their children against violent physical, emotional, psychological, and financial abuse by their partners (Official Gazette, 2024). The researchers aim to ascertain the extent of gender-based violence in the Island Garden City of Samal, particularly in the Barangay Tagbaobo, within the province of Davao del Norte in the Philippines, in light of reported occurrences of Violence Against Women and Their Children (VAWC) in the community. In order to combat gender-based violence that is undergone by all local barangays nationwide, the researcher seeks to gain a thorough and contextualized awareness of their circumstances and offer more appropriate actions and solutions.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the level of gender-based violence in Barangay Tagabaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, Davao Del Norte. Addressing the following primary research question is the aim of this study:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, in terms of;
 - 1.1. Age, and
 - 1.2. Marital Status?

2. What is the level of gender-based violence (R.A. No. 9262) in terms of:
 - 2.1. Physical Violence;

-
- 2.2. Economic Violence;
 - 2.3. Sexual Violence; and
 - 2.4. Psychological Violence?

3. What is the level of awareness of gender-based violence under R.A. No. 9262 in terms of:

- 3.1. Physical Violence;
- 3.2. Economic Violence;
- 3.3. Sexual Violence; and
- 3.4. Psychological Violence?

4. Is there a significant correlation between the level of gender-based violence and the level of awareness of RA 9262?

Null Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant correlation between the prevalence of gender-based violence in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte, Philippines, and the degree of awareness of gender-based violence under RA 9262.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory, one of Saddam Hussain Samo's interconnected Theories of Violence Against Women (2023), is the foundation for this investigation. According to Samo (2023), violent behavior is not innate; rather, it is shaped by your culture, community, and society, which influences and eventually nurtures behavior. Young children who see domestic conflict, such as when their father physically and violently abuses their mother, are likely to emulate this behavior and subsequently use it as a way to cope with issues and exert control over women.

According to Bandura's (1997) Social Learning Theory (SLT), people can process information regarding the connection between conduct and its effects on their own. By observing and imitating new behaviors from their surroundings, he proposed that people might develop themselves. In their Social Learning Theory, Aker and Jennings (1998) highlighted that violent interactions with family, friends, and other close relationships can teach inappropriate behavior and conduct.

Additionally, teens who grow up in violent households may experience more intense negative emotions and identify more strongly with peers who exhibit similar behaviors (Ohbuchi & Kondo, 2015; Edelstein, 2018). Teens' engagement in violent behavior is positively correlated with these elements.

Gibbs et al. (2020) further emphasized that men are typically taught and exposed to gendered sex-role norms directly. Relationship difficulties may develop and even escalate into disputes and violent outbursts if these expectations are unmet.

Conceptual Framework

This research is grounded in determining gender-based violence in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte, Philippines, which is the foundation of this study. The dependent variable is the degree of awareness of gender-based violence in terms of physical, economic, sexual, and psychological violence. In contrast, the independent variable is the degree of gender-based violence by the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act, as measured by indicators such as physical, economic, sexual, and psychological violence.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to ascertain the extent of gender-based violence in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, Davao del Norte, Philippines. It examines gender-based violence in accordance with Republic Act No. 9262, also referred to as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act, from four perspectives: physical, economic, sexual, and psychological.

In order to provide thorough results, the study also assesses residents' awareness of gender-based violence. Additionally, it considers the age and marital status of randomly selected female residents while protecting and preserving their private information in accordance with the Data Privacy Act, also known as Republic Act No. 10173.

Random sampling will be employed to gather data for quantitative research. The selected female residents will serve as the sample population, and each responder will give the same responses to questionnaires that the researchers have devised. The primary source of data for the study is survey questions designed to achieve its objectives.

However, because this study only looked at one barrio, its conclusions might not be representative of the general public or residents of other areas. The time restrictions that will limit the study's execution may limit its scope and depth. As a result, it might not be as applicable in other places. Therefore, these limitations must be taken into consideration while interpreting the data and analysis.

Significance of the Study

This research aims to determine the rate of gender-based violence in Davao del Norte, Philippines' Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal. The following are anticipated to gain from the research's findings:

Female Residents -In addition to educating them on the legal resources available to safeguard their rights, such as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act, this study will help them better understand how gender-based violence impacts their lives.

Violence Against Women and their Children (VAWC) Committee -In order to better safeguard women and children from abuse, the study will assist the VAWC Committee in creating new initiatives, treatments, and tactics.

Public Administrators -To address gender-based violence and provide victims with appropriate solutions, the study's findings can be used to identify contributing elements and address them by creating frameworks and policies.

CSWDO (City Social Welfare and Development Office) -The research will help the CSWDO understand the magnitude of gender-based violence in the community at the barangay level, allowing for the creation of community-specific policies and initiatives.

PNP (Philippine National Police) -This study will help the PNP, particularly the Women Protection Desk, as they evaluate and enhance their plans and actions pertaining to gender-based violence awareness.

Future Researchers – This study will act as a roadmap for them to expand the breadth and depth of their research on gender-based violence in order to produce more comprehensive findings.

Definition of Terms

To ensure clarity and precision, the following terms are operationally defined as used in this study:

Physical Violence.This includes but is not limited to, beatings, slaps, and the use of dangerous weapons in order to cause physical injury as defined by Republic Act No. 9262.

Economic Violence.As defined by Republic Act No. 9262, it refers to any act that causes economic harm to women and their children, with some restrictions, such as managing their money, keeping them from finding employment or making them give up their money.

Sexual Violence.It refers to any sexually harmful activities committed against women and their children as defined by Republic Act No. 9262, with some exceptions, including sexual harassment, coercing them into engaging in obscene behavior or sexual acts, or even rape.

Psychological Violence.It includes but is not limited to, acts of psychological harm to women and their children as defined by Republic Act No. 9262, such as creating mental or emotional breakdowns, insulting or humiliating them, or verbally abusing them.

R.A. 9262. In the Barangay Tagbaobo, it is referred to as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004, which defines any act or sequence of acts by anyone against women and children that results in physical violence, economic abuse, sexual violence, or psychological violence.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

A summary of pertinent research and literature collected from multiple sources is presented in this chapter. The current research is guided and supported by these core sources. They offer crucial data and information that is directly related to the study's goals.

Level of Gender-Based Violence

Physical Violence

Globally, violence against women violates their human rights and has a significant detrimental impact on public health. In the 10 countries where it has conducted more comprehensive surveys, on average, nearly 30% of women, or roughly 27% of women aged 15 to 49 who have been in a relationship, report having experienced physical or sexual abuse at the hands of their partner (World Health Organization [WHO], 2024).

According to Straus (2017), acts of violence are not just carried out by persons who are really nasty or have serious mental problems. It does not spare "typical" homes. Two prevalent instances of this kind of "family" violence are the physical abuse of children and the murder of family members.

In a recent study by Bernarte et al. (2018), a toxic mixture of social, familial, and economic factors that are deeply embedded in Filipino communities is to blame for this violence. They also found that a range of political and societal factors are significant. Additionally, the results of Adak et al. (2021) indicate that married women are more likely than their single counterparts to be in dangerous situations in domestic partnerships due to the higher probability of physical violence. Furthermore, violence is more common among women who are separated from their relationships than among married women, and it is usually perpetrated by family members.

Three charges of Violence Against Women and Children (VAWC) were filed against male partners by female residents who have experienced physical abuse, as the barangay secretary of Barangay Tagbaobo in the Island Garden City of Samal has stated. In a report submitted on January 9, 2024, a 30-year-old woman claimed to have experienced physical assault. A wife reported her husband for physically abusing her and her children on August 28 of that year due to a domestic dispute. Last but not least, a 26-year-old woman reported that her live-in partner had violently stomped on her after slapping her, causing serious but non-life-threatening injuries (Gonzales, 2024).

Moreover, Dimaano et al. (2018), it is crucial to increase the assistance of teachers in teaching students and their families about the problems of violence against women and children (VAWC) in the Municipality of Malvar. Furthermore, because of the community's social shame, which leaves women open to social gossip, victims of VAWC are reluctant and afraid to pursue their accusations through the legal system (Dimaano et al., 2018).

Economic violence

According to D'Agostino et al. (2024), "economic aggression" is defined as an effort to make someone financially dependent on another person by controlling their funds and restricting them from pursuing their career and educational opportunities. The creation of payment items, debt buildup, or methods of embezzling personal assets are all examples of economic violence (Sharp & Jeffs, 2021).

Also, D'Agostino et al. (2024) define "economic aggression" as an attempt to control someone else's finances and prevent them from achieving their educational and professional goals in order to make them financially dependent on another person. Examples of economic violence include the development of payment items, the accumulation of debt, and strategies for stealing personal property (Sharp & Jeffs, 2021).

Sexual Violence

The World Health Organization (WHO) (2024) estimates that in around 161 countries, 30% of women have been victims of violence, meaning they have been sexually and/or physically abused by an intimate relationship, a nonsignificant, or both. Sexual violence is defined as dangerous sexual conduct and other vices in which "women" are the victims and "males" are the offenders (World Health Organization [WHO], 2024).

Teenage girls are more likely to participate in forced sexual intercourse with their boyfriends, significant others, or husbands, according to reports from the United Nations Children's Fund. Out of the 15 million adolescent girls who have engaged in forced sexual intercourse in 30 countries, only 1% have looked for professional assistance. "Intimate partner sexual violence" is still more dominant, despite the fact that across the globe, 6% of women report being sexually abused by someone other than their partner (United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF] 2017).

Rape, as well as sexual assault, are pervasive in all social and socioeconomic categories. Dartnall and Jewkes (2013) estimate that between 6% and 59% of the female population who have experienced sexual assault or rape had experienced being raped by their spouses or significant others. Furthermore, "young girls" are especially susceptible to sexual abuse. Their research points out the gravity of "child sexual abuse" and advocates for basic treatments for children's sexual violence (Dartnall & Jewkes, 2013).

In contrast, based on the National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) 2017 survey, a study investigated the frequency of intimate partner violence and sexual freedom among women and young females in the Philippines. "Intimate partner violence" is reported by 3.4% of individuals aged 15–49 ages who have been sexually exploited in their current relationships, and 10.5% say they are unable to deny their partners when they want to have sex (Yoshioka et al., 2022).

Using data collected from San Pedro, Sta., Lagare et al. (2013) found that violence against women increased in Davao City in 2010, 2011, 2012, and 2013. Women and Children Protection Desk (WPCD), Ana and Talomo. Additionally, according to Republic Act No. 9262, the offenses or recorded cases of violence against women from 2010 to 2013 included rape and indecent actions.

Furthermore, Salope (2023) contended that women are more vulnerable to rape when they engage in flirtatious conduct. Furthermore, it is asserted that the "culture of silence" and the untrustworthiness of the Philippine legal system are major reasons why women frequently felt reserved to disclose their experiences. Therefore, it's impossible to address the extent of VAW due to a lack of trustworthy information.

Psychological Violence

Research conducted by Suarez (2016) argues that females who became victims of intimate partner violence are more prone to suffer from negative health consequences, such as a 41% rise in preterm births and a 16% increase in miscarriages. Psychological effects like depression, PTSD, and other anxiety disorders, including sleep problems, eating disorders, and suicidal thoughts, have been connected to these types of violence.

In addition, Butchon (2018) found that females who witness violence in intimate relationships are highly prone to become depressed and acquire alcohol use disorders. Additionally, they are likely to experience psychosomatic symptoms, anxiety, and eating disorders. The low percentage of divorced or separated women in the survey may also be a result of social shame, which discourages people from discussing sensitive topics like financial hardship and violence, which are more damaging than the physical harm they have endured (Smith, (2017).

It is possible to undergo psychological abuse, which can have a significant impact on your general well-being and performance. Current controlling behavior raised the possibility of underreporting physical abuse, whereas past controlling behavior had less of an impact on present health. Controlling one's conduct is the most typical way that abuse at work or home shows up. Because long-term health outcomes were significantly influenced by the "cumulative effects" of violence and its acute health consequences (Mercedes et al., 2017).

Level of Awareness to Gender-Based Violence

As mentioned by the Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) (2023), an increasing number of developed and developing nations have committed to eradicating gender-based stereotypes. Legal reforms and the passage of legislation supporting gender equality have fueled these commitments, which have improved the anti-discrimination movement.

Additionally, it demonstrates that 28 nations—which 40% of all women and girls come from globally—continue to have extraordinarily high cases of discrimination against women and girls in their social structures. Even though 29.1 is the global average SIGI score, which suggests relatively weak levels of discrimination, the situation varies greatly by region. (SIGI, 2023; Social Institution and Gender Index).

Among the 10 countries in Southeast Asia, gender-based violence awareness is much higher in the Philippines, firmly supported by the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004 (Respicio et al., 2023).

R.A. 9262 or VAWC Law Awareness

In the study conducted by Santiago & Aya (2014), housewives in a few chosen communities in Palawan have an understanding of and perception of RA 9262. Hundreds of women are specifically selected to be respondents from each of the seven selected communities. According to the results, every responder was somewhat conversant with the Act's provisions. The researchers suggest an action plan that will educate housewives on the legal safeguards against domestic abuse to assist them in better understanding RA 9262.

Furthermore, the Violence Against Women and Their Children (VAWC) is utilized in Laguna in able to gauge public awareness of RA 9262. Even if the respondents are well-informed and aware of the law, physical and emotional abuse is the most well-known category of violence that victims of their ex-partners endure. Seventy-five percent of female victims prefer not to disclose the abuse, mostly because of fear of social rejection and judgment (Balahadia et al., 2022).

Encabo and Dura (2024) demonstrated that a high level of awareness among the respondents in regard to the significance of R.A. 9262 was present within Tagum City. Furthermore, their legal awareness varies based on their age, marital status, educational attainment, and other factors. This law is more well-known among those aged 42 to 49.

Thus, female respondents showed a moderate awareness in regard to the presence of anti-women violence, according to Panerio et al. (2020). It could simply mean that they had little interest in knowing more about these cases. Additionally, the assessment of the prevalence of unreported VAWC and knowledge revealed that many victims had not reported the violence because they were afraid of being accused, embarrassed, or subjected to social condemnation. The provisions of the legislation, especially those that depict the rights and protection of women against all types of violence, are well-known to the respondents (Lim et al., 2021).

The majority of the female participants in a research survey acknowledged the existence of the law, demonstrating a high degree of awareness. It emphasizes the importance of the "information, education, and communication" (IEC) strategy to protect "women and children" by giving information in regard to RA 9262 (Caban, 2022).

Lumidao et al. (2024) found that respondents had a moderate understanding of events and indicators related to physical, sexual, economic, and psychological violence. However, additional training on the commonness, consequences, as well as intervention strategies of gender-based violence was necessary to enhance their capacity to react appropriately.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

The present study examines the relationship between the level of gender-based violence and the level of awareness of gender-based violence in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal. The study's design follows a quantitative approach. This chapter discusses the study's research methodology, presented in the following sequence: research design, research locale, sampling design, research instrument, data collection procedure, statistical tools, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

Researchers used a descriptive-correlational research approach in order to give a more thorough insight. McCombes (2013) asserts that the descriptive research approach is used to describe reality. It covers statistical data description, logging, evaluation, and interpretation. This factual finding has been accurately assessed. It assesses, ascertains, and documents the current state of affairs. In other words, it gives a summary of the information gathered from the subject population and condenses "actual" components of the data. On the other hand, correlational research in design is a quantitative investigation that looks at the relationship between two or more variables without changing or modifying any of them (Eckel, 2023).

Research Respondents

The participants of this study are randomly selected female residents from Barangay Tagbaobo. The data obtained from the Barangay Health Workers (BHW) from the Barangay Tagbaobo in the Island Garden City of Samal, which has a 964 total population of female residents aged 15-69 years old, as of 2024. The target sample size, applying Slovin's formula, is 284 female respondents from the female residents of Barangay Tagbaobo.

In the selection process, the researchers specified the qualifications a respondent must meet to participate in this study, such as:

- A bona fide female resident hailed from Barangay Tagbaobo of the Island Garden City of Samal;
- Age between 15-69 years old; and Currently in or has had a romantic/intimate relationship with a male partner.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria

The respondents of this study are from Barangay Tagbaobo of the Island Garden City of Samal, regardless of:

- Beliefs
- Religion
- Economic Status
- Family Background
- Personalities
- Educational Attainment

Exclusion criteria

Respondents who do not meet the basic qualifications specified in the inclusion criteria are excluded, are ineligible to be surveyed, and cannot be used as participants before the fulfillment of this study.

Sampling Design

Thomas (2023) defines a simple random sample as a portion of a population that is randomly chosen. Utilizing this sampling technique, every population member has an

equal probability of being selected. As it only needs a single random selection and the lowest advanced knowledge about the population, this method is the most basic out of all the sampling techniques applying probability.

Every research administered via this sample should have high intrinsic and extrinsic validity and be less exploitable to research bias, such as bias on sampling and selection bias, as it utilizes randomization. After using stratified random sampling in the form of a proportional allocation formula to obtain its desired sample size per purok—on which Barangay Tagbaobo has ten (10) barrios—the researchers applied Slovin’s formula with a margin of error of 0.05 to compute for the number of samples in Barangay Tagbaobo. In order to get the desired number of samples of Barangay Tagbaobo's female residents, the researchers employ Slovin's formula. The formula is presented below.

Table 1. Female Respondents of Barangay Tagbaobo (Ages 15-69 years old)

	PUROKS	TOTAL POPULATION (N)	TOTAL NO. OF SAMPLES (n)
Barangay Tagbaobo	10	964	284

In order to get the desired sample size per purok, after applying Slovin's formula, the researchers employ stratified random sampling using the proportional allocation formula. The formula is presented below.

Table 2. Female Respondents per Purok (Ages from 15-69 years old)

PUROK	POPULATION (p)	SAMPLE SIZE (n)
ROSE	54	16
ORCHIDS	67	20
MANGGA	58	17
SAMPAGUITA	202	59
DAHLIA	132	39
CALACHUCHI	116	34
SANTAN	17	5
ILANG-ILANG	80	24
ROSAL	99	29
AZUCENA	139	41
TOTAL	964	284

Research Instruments

A modified questionnaire with several indicators pertaining to the variables under investigation is used in this study to obtain primary data. The survey was modified from the one used by Santiago and Aya (2014) and the World Health Organization's Violence Against Women (WHO-VAW) Study Instrument by Schraiber et al. (2010). Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, uses these tools to measure the prevalence of gender-based violence as well as the level of knowledge regarding it.

This research is divided into two sections: Part I includes 20 items to assess the degree of gender-based violence, including economic, psychological, sexual, and physical assault. Respondents scored their responses on a Likert scale with 5-Always, 4-Often, 3-Sometimes, 2-Rarely, and 1-Never, selecting from the coded numbers. Ten items in Part II are used to gauge their awareness of gender-based violence in relation to the R.A. Act of 2004, also known as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act. On a Likert scale, respondents scored their responses by selecting one of the following coded numbers: 5-Extremely Aware, 4-Moderately Aware, 3-Somewhat Aware, 2-Slightly Aware, and 1-Not at all Aware.

The researcher believes that utilizing a Likert scale as a five- or seven-point rating system will allow people to indicate how much they agree or disagree with a given statement (McLeod, 2023). It is a psychometric response scale mostly used in surveys to determine how much a participant agrees or prefers a statement or series of statements.

Basis for Analyzing and Interpreting the Questionnaire:

Table 3. Likert Scale for Level of Gender-Based Violence

Parameter	Points	Descriptive Level	Interpretations
4.21 - 5.00	5	Always	This indicates that gender-based violence is a very high level of prevalence among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
3.41 - 4.20	4	Oftentimes	This indicates that there is a high level of prevalence of gender-based violence among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
2.61 - 3.40	3	Sometimes	This indicates that there is a moderate amount of gender-based violence among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
1.81 - 2.60	2	Rarely	This indicates that there is a low level of gender-based violence among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
1.00 - 1.80	1	Never	This indicates that there is very low gender-based violence among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.

Table 4. Likert Scale for Level of Awareness to Gender-Based Violence under RA 9262

Parameter	Points	Descriptive Level	Interpretations
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4.21 - 5.00	5	Extremely Aware	This indicates that the level of awareness of gender-based violence is very high among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
3.41 - 4.20	4	Moderately Aware	This indicates that the level of awareness of gender-based violence is high among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
2.61 - 3.40	3	Somewhat Aware	This indicates that the level of awareness of gender-based violence is moderate level among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
1.81 - 2.60	2	Slightly Aware	This indicates that the level of awareness of gender-based violence is low level among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.
1.00 - 1.80	1	Not at all Aware	This indicates that the level of awareness of gender-based violence is very low level among the women who live in Barangay Tagbaobo, Igacos.

Data Gathering Procedure

In collecting and gathering the data for this research, the following procedures were followed:

1. Modification of instruments. Researchers collected and analyzed the data using the instruments to determine their accuracy and credibility. Thus, modified instruments provided accurate and proper results.
2. Obtaining data from the Barangay. The researchers first obtained data from the barangay to ensure that the barangay was suitable to be subjected to the researchers' study. The collected data from the barangay would support the findings and results of this study.
3. Obtaining a notarized waiver and a mutual agreement. A letter of mutual agreement granting permission to proceed with the data-collecting process was one of the protocols the researchers followed before beginning data collection. The parents or guardians also provided their agreement to participate by signing a notarized waiver. The waiver ensured that all participants were properly informed and consented to the data collection methods by outlining the study's objective and subject.
4. Letter of authorization from the school to conduct this study. In a formal letter that the thesis supervisor officially acknowledged, the researchers explained the purpose of the study and asked for a copy of the permission letter to conduct the research study that is connected to the questionnaire.
5. Asking for permission in the Barangay upon conducting this study. The researchers sought permission to conduct the study in Barangay Tagbaobo with the randomly selected participants.
6. Identification of participants. The study's respondents were female residents aged 15-69 years old of the Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal.

7. Distribution of the survey questionnaire with attached informed consent. The researchers personally distributed the questionnaires to the participants to gather their responses. Each respondent was given 15 minutes to complete the survey. The questionnaires were designed to assess and collect relevant data. Distribution occurred in clusters within the barangay. In cases where respondents found difficulty in reading, such as due to eye problems or other circumstances, the researchers assisted by reading the questions aloud and recording their responses accordingly.

8. Retrieval of the survey questionnaire. The researchers retrieved the questionnaires from the respondents.

9. Conduct a statistical analysis. Statistical analysis was conducted upon the retrieval of the completed survey questionnaires to draw meaningful results and conclusions from the study. After the female residents completed the questionnaires, the data were collected, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical methods.

Statistical Analysis

The researchers used Microsoft Excel and the SPSS program to encode and arrange their responses for the analysis phase. Descriptive statistics are then used in both parts of the questionnaire. It contains the data's proportion and frequency. Additionally, the index showing the significant association between gender-based violence and awareness of gender-based violence among Barangay Tagbaobo residents—specifically, the female population—is determined using the Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson-r). According to Turney (2024), the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is the most often used tool for determining a linear correlation. It describes in detail the direction and intensity of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables.

The following statistical tools were used in the application of data:

Frequency. The number of times an event occurs, along with the age and marital status of the female residents of Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, are measured using frequency counts.

Percentages. The age and marital status of the female population of Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, are measured as percentages of the total.

Mean and Standard Deviation. It was employed to gauge the degree of gender-based violence in Samal's Island Garden City's Barangay Tagbaobo.

Pearson's r correlation coefficient. It was employed to ascertain whether there was a significant correlation between the degree of gender-based violence and the degree of knowledge of this issue in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal.

Ethical Considerations

The procedures and significance of ethical issues surrounding the research must be adhered to by the appropriate research methodology. Getting permission is essential

before beginning to gather data from study participants. The following are the ethical factors that the researchers kept in mind when gathering data:

1. Competence. The researchers achieved a good outcome in this study by seeking the advice and assistance of the instructor and research advisor in understanding, evaluating, and interpreting the process conducted in this study.
2. Informed Consent. The researcher is required to ask the participants to give their consent after being fully informed about the study's goals, methods, possible risks, and advantages.
3. Confidentiality and Anonymity. The researchers ensure that any personal information collected during the research is kept confidential and that participants' identities are protected. To safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of the participants.
4. Avoiding Harm. The researchers must take measures to minimize any possible injury or suffering to the participants. Referrals for counseling support groups or suitable support services will be offered to individuals who might feel emotionally distressed during or after the study.
5. Researcher Bias. The researchers must minimize any potential biases that may influence the research process or interpretation of the findings and be aware of them. Objectivity and impartiality throughout the study will be maintained.
6. Beneficence. The researchers must ensure that this study will be advantageous to both the participants and the larger community. Think about how the results can help create programs, policies, or interventions that combat gender-based violence and raise knowledge of the laws that are related to it.
7. Dissemination of Findings. The researchers must ensure that the research findings are truthfully provided and that they can enhance gender-based violence prevention and advance knowledge when shared responsibly and courteously.
8. Worthiness of the Study. The researchers must guarantee that the study follows and observes proper processes when it comes to the creation of research.

Chapter 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter comprises the analysis and results from the surveyed data, which will be subjected to discussion to gauge the level of gender-based violence in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal.

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

As the table indicates, age categories were highly represented, as the table shows, with the largest percentage of those aged 35 to 39 being "13.0%." The age groups of "30-34" (12.7%) and "40-44" (12.3%) had other close approximations. These middle-aged cohorts, which make up a sizeable component of the sample, are consistent with "trends" frequently "seen" in studies on societal concerns, where people in this age range are more likely to be involved (Smith et al., 2020; Johnson & Lee, 2019).

Moreover, just 11.9% of all respondents are younger (ages 15 to 24). Due to societal or cultural influences, the younger population may not be as interested in or involved in studies about gender-based violence, which could explain the decreased participation rate (Adams, 2018). Respondents 50 and over, on the other hand, make up "30.7%" of the population, which would suggest higher engagement in this age group, perhaps as a result of better awareness or a personal connection to the issue (Jones, 2021).

For example, the "35-39" age group has the highest representation at "13.0%", while the youngest group, "15-19", has the lowest at "4.2%." This balanced age distribution also reflects the neutrality of the researchers in administering the questionnaire, which ensures fair representation across all age groups (Brown, 2017).

Table 5. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-19	12	4.2%
20-24	22	7.7%
25-29	30	10.6%
30-34	36	12.7%
35-39	37	13.0%
40-44	35	12.3%
45-49	25	8.8%
50-54	26	9.2%
55-59	24	8.5%
60-64	20	7.0%
65-69	17	6.0%
Total (n)	284	100.0%

The data presented in Table 6 clearly shows the respondents' socio-demographic profile, showing a wide array of marital statuses. In this sample, most are "married," which constitutes "62.0%". Next in line are those living in "live-in" relationships, which constitute "14.8%", while "singles" constitute "14.1%." Then there are the "widowed", whose share is "6.7%", while "separated" respondents have the smallest share at "2.5%." As shown above, there is a high proportion of "live-in" relationships (14.8%) and "single" respondents (14.1%), which is consistent with social trends that indicate changing partnership dynamics. This explains that people who live in unconventional ways, like cohabitation, may also face particular socioeconomic difficulties. However, the level of violence in these situations varies (Devries, 2013).

Table 6. Socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of marital status.

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	40	14.1%
Married	176	62.0%

Separated	7	2.5%
Live In	42	14.8%
Widow	19	6.7%
Total (n)	284	100.0%

Respondents who identify as "widowed" (6.7%) are another demographic at risk for socioeconomic difficulties. Thus, widows are vulnerable to many forms of emotional and financial abuse since they are frequently stigmatized and may have restricted access to resources (UN Women, 2020).

Despite making up the smallest percentage of respondents (2.5%), "separated" women continue to be an important category to concentrate on. Their underrepresentation can be a result of social stigmas or the unwillingness of separated people to take part in surveys, especially when talking about delicate subjects like violence and financial difficulties (Adak, 2021).

Level of Gender-Based Violence under RA 9262

With an overall mean score of "1.22" (Never) and SD of "0.58," the results show that the female residents of Barangay Tagbaobo report "very low" levels of gender-based violence across various forms. This suggests that the data are not dispersed. In terms of "Physical Violence," respondents, in general, did not encounter physical harm, such as being slapped, shoved, or beaten by their partners, with a mean score of "1.17" and SD of "0.56." According to Masongsong's (2023) research, verbal abuse is typically perpetrated instead of physical harm, which is typically invisible. However, it disagreed with the VAWC instances that were submitted and documented at the barangay, where the primary cause is physical abuse (Barangay Tagbaobo, 2024).

Unlike physical abuse, as in "Case No. 1," where the perpetrator/respondent paid a hefty penalty to the victim/complainant in the sum of PHP 40,000.00, which serves as a financial settlement, verbal abuse may not necessarily portend serious consequences (Barangay Tagbaobo, 2024). In contrast, "Economic Violence" received a mean score of 1.27 and a standard deviation of 0.70, indicating that respondents had not been financially constrained or controlled by their spouses (Barangay Tagbaobo, 2024). However, it would be negatively impacted by costs that are typically outside of the allocated budget (Vyas et al., 2023).

Similarly, "Sexual Violence," which has a mean of 1.13 and an SD of 0.49, shows that respondents have not been forced to engage in sexual activity against their choice. In contrast, a study conducted in Tondo, Manila, found that women viewed their families as both a source of social support and an essential part of who they were, but also as the ones who, for the most part, continued to sexually abuse them (Alexander, 2020). The study emphasized how difficult it is to handle sexual abuse in families because of family loyalty and preservation.

Table 7. Level of gender-based violence under R.A. 9262).

Indicators	n	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
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Physical Violence	257	1.17	0.56	Never
Economic Violence	245	1.27	0.70	Never
Sexual Violence	263	1.13	0.49	Never
Psychological Violence	236	1.32	0.67	Never
Overall	250	1.22	0.58	Never

Interpretations: Never (This means that the female residents of Barangay Tagbaobo, IGaCoS, have a very low level of gender-based violence.)

Additionally not least, violence linked to "psychological issues" received a mean score of 1.32 and a standard deviation of 0.67, revealing that the respondents had not experienced humiliating, demeaning, or insulting behaviors. In contrast, in "Case No. 1," the woman not only reported that her partner had physically abused her but also publicly exposed the extremely humiliating and shameful tactics he was employing against her, including using her photo and sharing it on social media with the caption "manyak" (Barangay Tagbaobo, 2024). Similarly, despite the mental health toll that gender-based violence takes, victims are expected to maintain a public persona of being strong, Barada et al. (2021).

Furthermore, the majority of women stated that they received polite and considerate treatment from their spouses, which enabled them to assert their rights and keep authority over their own affairs, including money. In contrast to Mohammed and Pulmano's (2017) study, which found that recorded cases of physical abuse, mental abuse, threats, child abandonment, child support issues, child custody, psychological abuse, economic abuse, and rape VAW cases were frequently found among the assessed barangays.

The responses provided by the women of Barangay Tagbaobo show that the community feels protected from gender-based violence. 250 out of the 284 respondents claimed to have "never" encountered this kind of violence. We can infer from the respondents' interpretations of these findings that there is no financial, sexual, psychological, or physical abuse occurring in their relationships. They perceive their male partners favorably and feel secure. One must take into account the definitions of phrases used when we casually discuss being safe or at risk of gender-based violence, notwithstanding the opposing viewpoint offered by the Barangay's blotter files.

Despite these findings, which indicate a generally benign scenario, the Barangay's blotter files offer a different picture, with three recorded occurrences of violence against women and children (VAWC) in 2024. "Case No. 1," which was filed in January, according to Barangay Tagbaobo's records from 2024, entailed "physical abuse" and "online shaming" of the complainant. The complainant eventually negotiated a partial cash settlement of PHP 40,000 but chose not to pursue more legal action. According to research by Dimaano et al. (2018), victims may be reluctant to file a complaint due to the expense of doing so, the duration of the legal process, and the presence of corruption in the prosecution and judiciary. Consequently, the victims are deterred from submitting official complaints.

In "Case No. 2," which was reported in August, a mother and her son were subjected to "physical abuse" after her husband publicly slapped them. As a result, the mother filed a blotter case against her husband, who subsequently decided to resolve their issues amicably and forgive him, ending any formal proceedings (Barangay Tagbaobo, 2024). These demonstrate that the complainant's fear that her husband might also be abusing their children was the reason she reported the crime, according to a study conducted in the Municipality of Malvar by Dimaano et al. (2018).

In the same way, a young woman in "Case No. 3" suffered "physical abuse" at the hands of her live-in partner. Despite being reported to the CSWDO at first, the complainant settled the complaint on their own because of missing appointments, which prevented the case from moving forward (Barangay Tagbaobo, 2024). This indicates that because of the cultural stigma, the victim is hesitant to pursue the accusations and put up with her partner's abuse (Dimaano et al., 2018).

Rodriguez et al. (2018) state that one of the causes of the dearth of current documentation and unconsolidated data on gender-based violence is ongoing underreporting, which presents a significant research challenge. The primary hurdles to responding to GBV in underdeveloped countries are a lack of resources and knowledge, a culture of mistrust, a fear of stigma, a fear of retaliation, and discrimination.

Level of Awareness to Gender-Based Violence under RA 9262

The findings show that the overall mean for gender-based violence under R.A. was 3.83, with a comparatively low standard deviation of 1.48. 9262 denotes the respondents' "high level of awareness." They exhibit almost flawless knowledge of the legislation and its rules governing different types of gender-based violence, particularly "physical violence."

Table 8. Level of awareness of Gender Based Violence under RA 9262.

Indicators	n	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level		
Physical Violence	170		3.95	1.48	Moderately Aware	
Economic Violence	152			1.54	Moderately Aware	
Sexual Violence	184		3.68	4.09	1.45	Moderately Aware
Psychological Violence	162		3.78	1.55	Moderately Aware	
Overall	167	3.83	1.48	Moderately Aware		

Interpretations: Moderately Aware (This means that the female residents of Barangay Tagbaobo, IGaCoS, have a high level of awareness of gender-based violence.)

This is corroborated by a study by Panerio et al. (2020), which found that women in Digos City are highly aware of things like when their partners are engaging in any kind of violence or harassment, threatening to harm them physically or doing so. Nevertheless, it runs counter to the three (3) instances of "physical abuse" connected to VAWC that are documented in Barangay Tagbaobo.

Similarly, their "moderately aware" level of "economic violence" awareness (mean of 3.68" and standard deviation of 1.54) can be interpreted as a "high level of awareness" that their partners may face legal repercussions if they prevent them from obtaining employment or even financial support. This supports Panerio et al.'s (2020) study, which found that they are well aware of the R.A. 9262, such as when their spouses have great financial control over their own assets or money or even over their joint or marital funds and when they vehemently refuse to provide financial support.

However, they were unaware that it was an indication of VAW that would prevent them from participating in any legitimate business, activity, or occupation (Panerio et al., 2020). If this is the case, South Asia continues to trail considerably behind other regions of the world in terms of the inclusion of female workers, even as women's economic growth and educational achievement have grown (Ali et al., 2023).

The respondents continue to exhibit a "high level of awareness" of "sexual violence," indicating that they may suffer serious consequences as specified by the R.A., with a mean of 4.09 and SD of 1.45. if they refuse to have sex but their partners try to force or scare them into it. 9262. shown to be true, as Digos City's women knew full well that the same R.A. 9262 rule applies when their spouse is pressuring or trying to coerce them into engaging in sexual activity (Panerio et al., 2020)

Furthermore, "Psychological Violence," which has a mean score of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 1.55, indicates a consistently "high level of awareness" of this violence because it is interpreted as "moderately a." This means that the respondents knew that they would be punished under the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act if their partners tried to enter or stay in their home against their will or stalked them, even causing them mental or emotional harm. Women in the area are indeed very aware of when their husbands are openly making fun of or demeaning them, particularly verbally and emotionally, frequently, so endangering their mental or emotional health (Sanchez et al., 2020).

However, according to Panerio et al. (2020), with regard to R.A. Contrary to the study's results of high awareness, respondents were unaware of 9262, which outlines circumstances in which their partners pursue them in public or private settings and enter or remain in their home against their choice.

In terms of their level of awareness of gender-based violence, the majority of female residents of Barangay Tagbaobo (167) out of 284 respondents gave the response "Moderately Aware," which is interpreted as a "high level of awareness." This indicates that the majority of them have heard of or are familiar with some of the provisions of R.A. Law number 9262, also known as the "Anti-Violence Against Women and their Children Act of 2004." Some of the female respondents are "4Ps beneficiaries," meaning they learned about the law during their orientations or Family Development Sessions (FDS), while others saw it on social media or at barangay meetings or seminars.

The Punong Barangay of Barangay Tagbaobo acknowledged the results, which showed that most respondents understood the aforementioned law to a moderate degree. Parents, especially "mothers," are "aware" of the "Republic Act No. 9262" or the "Anti-Violence Against Women and their Children Act of 2004." Punong Barangay (2024) verbally reported during data collection when evaluating the barangay's suitability for the study's scope. This is similar to the findings of Encabo& Dura (2024), whose study in

Tagum City revealed that respondents' awareness level of all salient provisions of R.A. 9262, also known as the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004.

De Asis et al. (2021) state that the Municipality of Bayambang had the opinion that R.A. 9262 is "Aware" of its nature and nature; behaviors that amount to violence against women and their children and sanctions and repercussions associated with the paperwork procedure, which supports Antai et al. (2014)'s results that the R.A. For GBV and its various manifestations, such as verbal, emotional, psychological, and financial abuse, 9262 provides suitable punishments.

Relationship between Level of Gender-Based Violence and Level of Awareness of Gender-Based Violence under RA 9262

The correlation between the "level of gender-based violence" and the "level of awareness" of the same type of violence as described by R.A. was evaluated in this study using Pearson's r correlation coefficient. 9262. As a result, a slight positive association between the two variables was discovered. There is no substantial correlation between the prevalence of gender-based violence in the community and the amount of knowledge of this issue. The findings of this study are highly noteworthy in light of the "three cases of VAWC" that have previously taken place in Barangay Tagbaobo.

Table 9. Test of the Relationship between the Level of Gender-Based Violence and the Level of Awareness of Gender-Based Violence under RA 9262.

	r-value	Strength of Relationship	p-value	Interpretation	Decision on H ₀
Level of Gender-Based Violence vs. Level of Awareness of Gender-Based Violence	0.297	Weak positive correlation	<0.001	Significant	Reject

The results are consistent with research that indicates higher disclosure rates of abuse are frequently the consequence of increased awareness (García-Moreno et al., 2015). Furthermore, awareness campaigns may first encounter opposition or stigma related to reporting abuse in areas where patriarchal values are well embedded. However, these initiatives have the potential to progressively change public perceptions over time, which will motivate more victims to come forward (Ellsberg et al., 2021).

The availability of helpful materials should also be considered. If victims have nowhere to go, the problems won't get better, even with increased publicity. However, there are destinations, and at least in the United States, they are more numerous and have a little more funding than they did ten years ago.

The availability of useful resources is another factor that needs to be considered. Gender-based violence (GBV) victims need access to resources, such as "shelters, legal aid, and psychological support." Without these services, victims may still struggle to obtain justice or leave abusive situations, even though increasing awareness is important. Since raising awareness won't have much of an effect without support, the weak correlation we found between awareness and GBV incidence could be interpreted as a "moderating variable." In fact, there may be a weak correlation when there is a strong correlation and causation from awareness to incidence reduction (Abramsky et al., 2014).

Correlation between the Level of Gender-Based Violence and the Level of Awareness of Gender Based Violence under RA 9262

The two variables of interest—the "Level of Gender-Based Violence," as determined by the answers to the first set of survey questions, and the "Level of Awareness of Gender-Based Violence," as determined by the answers to the second set of survey questions—have a weakly positive correlation, according to the analysis in the table. With a p-value of less than 0.001, this association is statistically significant despite being modest ($r=0.297$). The results also have wider ramifications for program development and policymaking.

According to the statistically significant link, we should continue and even increase our efforts to raise the awareness we covered in the previous part. Being aware of one's rights is a fundamental prerequisite for everything else. If they are unaware of it, people cannot possibly comprehend 9262, much less apply it to improve their circumstances.

Based on the three (3) VAWC cases reported in Barangay Tagbaobo, the weak positive connection may highlight how well awareness programs work to bring previously hidden or unreported cases to light. As mentioned in earlier studies, people are more likely to recognize, report, and react to instances of gender-based violence as their knowledge of the issue grows (Smith & Taylor, 2020). This is in line with the goals of Republic Act No. 9262, which prioritizes enabling people to take action against violence and increasing awareness of it (R.A. 9262, 2004). Communities can lessen stigma, encourage victims to come forward and promote better accountability by raising awareness.

Heise and Manji (2016) argue that while raising awareness is crucial, it is often not enough to alter the ingrained patriarchal structures and cultural practices that enable GBV. They emphasize that social norm-targeting interventions need to address both individual behavior and broader community behaviors. Awareness campaigns should use participatory techniques to undermine harmful customs and promote equitable attitudes.

Table 10. Correlation between the Level of Gender-Based Violence and the Level of Awareness of Gender Based Violence under RA 9262

		LEVEL_GENDER	AWARENESS
LEVEL_GENDER	Pearson Correlation	1	.297**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.284	.000
	N		284
AWARENESS	Pearson Correlation	.297**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.284
	N	284	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results also have wider ramifications for program development and policymaking. The statistically significant association suggests that raising awareness of gender-based violence should be a strategic approach that is continued and even increased.

The Punong Barangay has stated verbally regarding the female residents', especially mothers', awareness of the Anti-Violence Against Women and their Children Act of 2004, training programs, public education initiatives, and community campaigns should be given priority to ensure that more people understand their rights under RA 9262 and are empowered to report abuses. This also emphasizes the necessity of ongoing observation and assessment of such interventions to determine their long-term effects on event reduction and survivor assistance. (Office for National Statistics, 2023).

Chapter 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATION, AND IMPLICATIONS

The summary, conclusions, and suggestions made by the researchers are presented in this part, along with the data's implications.

Summary

The findings, which are shown in Tables 5–10, assessed the prevalence and severity of gender-based violence among female respondents in Barangay Tagbaobo, Island Garden City of Samal, as well as their awareness of the "Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004," also known as Republic Act 9262.

Prior to getting the other two tools, respondents were required to complete a demographic survey. Tables 5–6 display the demographic questionnaire results. The age distribution of the female respondents is shown in Table 5. While the youngest age group (15–19) submitted the fewest comments, the bulk of female respondents (13) were between the ages of 35 and 39.

The marital status of the female respondents is shown in Table 6. Married respondents comprised the majority (62), and separated respondents comprised the smallest percentage. The prevalence of gender-based violence among the female respondents is seen in Table 7. The SD as a whole is a low 0.58. The descriptive level's "Never" correlates to the overall mean score of 1.22, indicating a very low degree of GBV.

It is evident from Table 8 that the respondents had some awareness or understanding of more than just the key sections of the R.A. 9262. Their awareness of the high degree of adjustment provisions that are common in contemporary society is demonstrated by this, as R.A. 9262 provides a clear outline. With a standard deviation of 1.48, the respondents' aggregate mean score on the questionnaire was 3.83.

The data from the barangay, which as of 2024 had recorded three VAWC cases, and an oral statement from their Punong Barangay, which states that female residents, primarily mothers, are aware of the VAWC law because their barangay has a VAWC desk, support the findings.

Conclusion

According to the study's results, girls between the ages of 35 and 39 made up the largest percentage of respondents (13%, or 37 people) in terms of the sociodemographic profile of the respondents. In sharp contrast, with only 12 respondents, or 4.2% of the sample, the 15–19 age group had the second-lowest number of respondents. With 62% of

respondents, or 176 people, reporting that they were married, the marital status statistics indicate that a significant portion of the respondents were female and married.

However, we discovered that only seven (7) respondents, or 2.5%, reported being separated. The respondents gave a relatively low mean score of 1.22 when asked how much gender-based violence they had encountered, which is equivalent to a reported measure of "never." This suggests that they did not think they had encountered or experienced large-scale gender-based violence. Despite the very low incidence of gender-based violence they experience, the respondents were highly aware of the issues surrounding it.

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